

Deliverable D9.9

Report on Dissemination and Communication activities. (3 | 4)

Deliverable report

Deliverable No.	D9.9	Work Package No.	WP9	Task/s No.	Tasks 9.1 & 9.2
Work Package Title	DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION AND EXPLOITATION				
Linked Task/s Title	Implementation of the Dissemination strategy, implementation of the Communication strategy, implementation of the Exploitation and IP strategy.				
Status	Final	(Draft/Draft Final/Final)			
Dissemination level	PU	(PU-Public, PP, RE-Restricted, CO-Confidential)			
Due date deliverable	2024-05-31	Submission date	2024-05-28		
Deliverable version	3				

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Document History

Version	Date	Comment
1	2024-05-01	First Version
2	2024- 05-21	Final version reviewed
3	2024- 05-28	Final version ready for submission

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DIGIECOQUARRY project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as a consequence of the project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policymakers) has been active since the beginning of the project identifying, analysing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analysed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allow a close follow-up of the main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them throughout the whole project activities. Among potential social risks, the impact on the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure the full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

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List of Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	DESCRIPTION
DEQ	DIGIECOQUARRY
DCEP	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan
WP	Work Package
D	Deliverable
RM	Raw Materials
EC	European Commission
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PC	Project Coordinator

1 Executive Summary

This report, titled '*D9.9: Report on dissemination and communication activities (3|4)*', displays all the dissemination and communication (D&C) activities that DIGIECOQUARRY beneficiaries have been carrying out between months 24 and 36 of the project to maximise its visibility and influence with the aim of:

- Effectively promote the project and its results to all target groups and audiences, both at national and European levels.
- Establish links and liaisons with international organisations and other interested stakeholders.
- Create synergies with other relevant projects and initiatives.
- Validate project outcomes to obtain feedback from expert groups, scientists and interested user communities.

All these actions are undertaken by WP9: *Implementation of The Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Strategy*. One of its goals is to design, execute, monitor and evaluate all the D&C activities. It considers specific actions and establishes the beneficiaries' responsibilities to ensure the project and its results are widely broadcast and reach the target audience.

DIGIECOQUARRY's assets and outcomes are conveyed in a meaningful way and tailored to each stakeholder group, to promote not only the project's results but also its vision and aim.

More detail on the topics to be disclosed as well as lists of identified stakeholders are included in *D9.1: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan*.

D&C strategies and actions are the cornerstones for generating a deep impact on DEQ's results when attracting the interest of the main stakeholders and social acceptance. To ensure this impact beyond the project lifetime, WP9 closely works with another two WPs: WP7. Mechanisms for social acceptance and interaction with policymakers and WP8. Clustering activities for a solid EU knowledge base on RM.

2 Dissemination and Communication activities

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 DEQ website's press releases

DEQ's website frequently releases press clips about its latest updates. They can be found in the 'news' section.

<https://digiecoquarry.eu/#news>

2.1.2 Articles in journals and magazines

Articles about the project have been written in different online magazines.

- ANEFA Actualidad by ANEFA:

<https://www.aridos.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/anefa-74-OK.pdf>

<https://www.aridos.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/anefa-75-baja-definitiva.pdf>

- Revista Anual de ANEFA (ANEFA's annual magazine):

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1L46R598gwHdCsdTff82AcpE--RfZhAoR/view>

2.1.3 Scientific publications (journals and congresses)

New scientific papers have been published between months 24 and 36 of the project.

Peer-reviewed journals

Asbjörnsson, G., Sköld, A., Zougari, S., Yar, A-G., Kamel, N., Turlur-Chabanon, S., Bhadani, K., Gowda, V., Lee, C., Hulthén, E., Evertsson, M. Development of Production and Environmental Platforms for the European Aggregates and Minerals Industries. Sustainable Minerals '23. (Chalmers University, AKKODIS, ROCTIM).

<https://www.min-eng.com/sustainableminerals23/drafts/session3/asbjornsson.pdf>

Marcos-Macías, F., Tamaki-Moreno, R., Cámara, M., Yagüe-Jiménez, V., Blanco Murillo, J.L. IA para el mantenimiento predictivo en canteras: Modelado. (UPM-AI).

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/375289583_IA_para_el_mantenimiento_predictivo_en_canteras_modelado

S. Gómez, JA. Sanchidrián, P. Segarra. (2024) Full-field solution from an oblique shock to estimate ground motion from blasting. International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences 176: 105688. (UPM-M).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijrmms.2024.105688>

Segarra, P., Sanchidrián, JA, Pötsch, M., Iglesias, L., Gómez, S., Gaich A., Bernardini, M. (2024). A Method for Reconstruction of Size Distributions from 3D Drone Image Analysis: A Case Study. Rock Mechanics and Rock Engineering. (UPM-M).

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00603-024-03765-1>

Cámara, MJ, Blanco, J.L., 2023 "Expanding the Frontiers of Web Audio With Autoencoders and JavaScript," J. Audio Eng. Soc., vol. 70, no. 11, pp. 979-989. (UPM-AI).

https://oa.upm.es/77104/1/JAES-D-22-00045_LR.pdf

Cámara, MJ., Blanco, J.L., 2023. Phase-Aware Transformations in Variational Autoencoders for Audio Effects. *J. Audio Eng. Soc.*, 70 (9), 731-741. (UPM-AI).

https://oa.upm.es/77103/1/JAES-D-22-00016_LR.pdf

Conference Proceedings

Li, En., Segarra, P., Khandelwal, M., Gómez, S., Monjezi, M., Zhou, J. 2023. A comparative study of backbreak distance prediction in the open-pit mine based on support vector regression and bio-inspired metaheuristic algorithms. *4th International Symposium of Machine Learning and Big Data in Geoscience*. University College Cork, Cork, Ireland, 29th August – 1st September 2023. Local Organising Committee for ISMLG 2023 (UPM-M).

Gómez, S., Sanchidrián, J. A., Segarra, P. 2023. JWL Equation of State applied to shock polar analysis. *12th World Conference on Explosives and Blasting, 9-12 September, Dublin*. European Federation of Explosives Engineers. (UPM-M).

Gómez S, Sanchidrián JA, Segarra P. 2023. Shock Impedance Method Applied to Detonation Pressure Measurements. *49th Annual Conference on Explosives and Blasting Technique*. San Antonio, TX, 6-7 February 2023. International Society of Explosives Engineers, pp. 345-351. (UPM_M).

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369040480_Shock_Impedance_Method_Applied_to_Detonation_Pressure_Measurements

Cámara Largo, M., Blanco Murillo, J.L. Foley-Vae: Generación de efectos de audio para cine con inteligencia artificial. *TECNIACÚSTICA 2023 (54ª International Conference of Acoustic Technologies)*. (UPM-AI).

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/375289585_FOLEY-VAE_GENERACION_DE_EFECTOS_DE_AUDIO_PARA_CINE_CON_INTELIGENCIA_ARTIFICIAL

M. Sánchez-Ruiz, L. Fernández-Galindo, J.D. Arias-Londoño, M.J.Cámara-Largo, G. Comini, A. Gabrys, J.L. Blanco-Murillo, J.I. Godino-Llorente, L.A. Hernández-Gómez. Del visual al auditivo: sonorización de escenas guiada por imagen. *TECNIACÚSTICA 2023 (54ª International Conference of Acoustic Technologies)*. (UPM-AI).

https://oa.upm.es/78660/1/paper_tecniacustica_maria.pdf

Ortiz, J.E., Plaza, P., Luaces, C., Herrero, J., Cabria, I., Blanco, J.L., Gavilanes, J., Escavy, J.I., López-Cilla, I., Yagüe, V., Pérez, C., Rodríguez, S., Rico, J., Serrano, C., Bernat, J., Romero, P., Viladés, L. (2023). La digitalización en las explotaciones de áridos. *XV International Congress on Energy and Minerals Resources*. (UPM-AI, SIGMA, ANEFA).

<https://www.sendaeventos.com/qrns/741428/docs/4042311092023203002.pdf>

Romero, P., Viladés, L., Luaces, C. Digitalización en la industria de los áridos. Implantación, usos y Casos de éxito. *XV International Congress on Energy and Minerals Resources 2023*. (ANEFA)

<https://www.sendaeventos.com/qrns/741428/docs/20882615112023134244.pdf>

Romero, P., Viladés, L., Luaces, C. Benchmarking y Cuadro de Mando Integral en el sector de los áridos. Traslado de las buenas prácticas y mejora continua. *XV International Congress on Energy and Minerals Resources 2023*. (ANEFA)

<https://www.sendaeventos.com/qrns/741428/docs/78708115112023134030.pdf>

Viladés, L., Romero, P., Luaces, C. DIGIECOQUARRY: el futuro del sector de los áridos ya es el presente. *XV International Congress on Energy and Minerals Resources 2023*. (ANEFA)

<https://www.sendaeventos.com/grns/741428/docs/7314915112023131557.pdf>

Berjano, S. El proyecto europeo H2020 – DIGIECOQUARRY en el marco estratégico del suministro de materias primas minerales. *XV International Congress on Energy and Minerals Resources 2023*. (DGAstur)

<https://www.sendaeventos.com/grns/741428/docs/5400320112023094517.pdf>

Lee, C., Sanchez Llanca, F., Asbjörnsson, G., & Evertsson, M. Application of Production Simulation Combined With Site-Specific Data To Quantify The Environmental Performance Of Aggregate Products At Five Pilot Sites. *Minerals Engineering 2024 Conference, Luleå, Sweden* (Chalmers)

https://research.chalmers.se/publication/540065/file/540065_Fulltext.pdf

S. Gómez, J.A. Sanchidrián, P. Segarra. 2024. A full-field solution to predict vibrations in the presence of a free surface. *Proc. 50th Annual Conference on Explosives and Blasting Technique*, Savannah, GA, 25-27 January 2024. International Society of Explosives Engineers, pp. 505-517.

2.1.4 Public deliverables

Those public deliverables that have been submitted and accepted by the European Commission have been uploaded on the project website: <https://digiecoquarry.eu/deliverables/>

2.1.5 Neutral Aggregates 2050

The aggregates sector's commitment to sustainability remains strong and achieves another important milestone on the road to Green Transition and decarbonisation. The Roadmap for Climate Neutrality in the Aggregates Industry: Neutral Aggregates 2050 demonstrates the companies' leadership regarding climate change adaptation and mitigation.

Figure 1. Neutral Aggregates 2050 cover and disclaimer.

Aggregates Europe - UEPG, as a member of the International Advisory Board, has contributed to the preparation and dissemination of this document through the approval of its Board and the launch under its umbrella in June 2023.

It can be read here: https://www.aggregates-europe.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/UEPG-Roadmap-on-Climate-Change-2023-1_compressed.pdf

2.2 Participation in congresses, events, trade fairs and workshops

Between months 24 and 36, DIGIECOQUARRY's consortium partners have participated in several external events to show their activities and results.

Besides, a list of identified events, fairs and workshops can be found in *D9.1 Annex XII*.

2.2.1 Tektónica fair

CIMPOR and DEQ were present at TEKTÓNICA – International Building and Construction Fair, the largest Portuguese Building and Construction Fair held in Lisboa on the first week of May 2023.

Figure 2. DEQ at Tektónica fair, Lisboa.

2.2.2 12th Concrete Pavement Congress

Asogras participated in the 12th Concrete Pavement Congress in May 2023, with a talk about the vision, challenges and trends in the aggregates industry. Carlos Forero, Director General, also highlighted the importance of projects such as DIGIECOQUARRY to contribute to the sustainability of the sector, digitalisation and automation as an innovative system in the exploitation of quarries.

Figure 3. DEQ at 12th Concrete Pavement Congress, Colombia.

2.2.3 26th World Mining Congress

During the 26th World Mining Congress, which took place in June 2023 in Brisbane, Australia, Montanuniversität Leoben presented how the project contributes to assess the environmental impact of the mining industry.

Figure 4. DEQ at the 26th World Mining Congress, Australia.

The following poster about Virtual Coring While Drilling, a technology under development in WP2 was also displayed.

Figure 5. DEQ poster at the 26th World Mining Congress, Australia.

2.2.4 Global Aggregates Information Network Summit

DEQ travelled along with ANEFA and ASOGRAVAS, as national Aggregates Associations representatives, and UEPG to Queenstown, New Zealand to be presented at the Global Aggregates Information Network annual meeting in July 2023.

This event brought together more than 45 delegates from 41 countries from all five continents, from 11 geographic areas, in addition to five more areas whose participation was carried out through online presentations. The Project Coordinator, César Luaces, also presented the Neutral Aggregates 2050 Roadmap on behalf of Aggregates Europe – UEPG.

Figure 6. DEQ at GAIN summit, New Zealand.

2.2.5 Expert Panel: New standards for circular economy in the construction industry

On the 25th of August, the Chalmers University team took part in a discussion on how standards can help/hinder producers in becoming more circular for the End-of-Waste network.

Figure 7. DEQ by Chalmers University, Sweden.

2.2.1 5° Internacional Concrete Sustainability Conference

The Colombian Chamber of Cement and Concrete PROCEMCO with the support of the Ibero-American Ready Mixed Concrete Federation FIHP, organized the fifth version of the International Concrete Sustainability Conference on the 28th and the 29th of August 2023 in Bogota, Colombia.

The conference offered learning and networking opportunities on the latest developments, technical expertise, ongoing research and solutions for sustainable concrete manufacturing, design and construction, and ASOGRAVAS presented DEQ.

Figure 8. DEQ at the International Concrete Sustainability Conference, Colombia.

2.2.2 Steinexpo

ITK attended Steinexpo 2023, the international demonstration fair for the raw materials and building materials industry that took place from the 23rd to the 26th of August at the MHI basalt quarry in Nieder-Ofleiden.

Figure 9. DEQ at Steinexpo, Germany.

2.2.3 IV Seminario Internacional de Minería y Planeamiento Minero

An event for the optimisation and good management of the different methods and technologies in the extractive sector was held in Medellín, Colombia, where ASOGRAVAS set up a stand.

Figure 10. DEQ at the IV Seminario Internacional de Minería y Planeamiento Minero, Colombia.

2.2.4 Euroschotter Conference

Euroschotter 2023 took place in Würzburg am Main in September 2023. Very valuable input concerning the economic situation, DEQ, the experience with EPDs in Spain, and the Neutral Aggregates Roadmap came from PC César Luaces Frades via online attendance.

TAGESORDNUNG EUROSCHOTTER 2023
14. bis 16. September 2023, Würzburg

Donnerstag, 14. September 2023	
15.30 Uhr	Abgüßungstermin
16.00 Uhr	Eröffnung und Begrüßung
	Nachhaltigkeit in der Rohstoffgewinnung - was will die Politik, was kann das Unternehmen
	Green Deal aus Sicht der Rohstoffindustrie (Dirk Finckh, UEPG)
	Die Säulen des EU Green Deal (Dr. Andreas Polter, Fachverband Stein und keramische Industrie)
	Spezialan: Politischer Anspruch und globale Realität
17.00 Uhr	Abschluss des Schwingenwörter des Historischen Gebäudes im Schloss Steinburg
Freitag, 15. September 2023	
09.00 Uhr	Fachtagung - 2. Teil
	Kundenblick zur wirtschaftlichen Lage
	Nachhaltigkeitsberichterstattung und Berichtspflichten
	Was sagen die Normen dazu? Prof. Dr.-Ing. Lutz Othar, Stuttgart
	Woher kommen die Daten zur Erstellung von EPDs? Dr. Eva Schmittke, BÜI
	Nachweise zur Quantifizierung von Nachhaltigkeitskriterien (Dipl.-Ing. Stefan Jansen, AMB)
	Fluss
	Über den Tellerrand - wie machen es andere (César Luaces Frades, span. Gesteinsverband Federación de Áridos)
	Umsetzung der Berichtspflichten zur Nachhaltigkeit - wer ist betroffen (Julian Rubin, WVA, WOLFF & MÜLLER ENERGY GMBH)
	EPDs für die schwedische Gesteinsbranche (Volker Witzig, FSKB)
	EPDs für die italien. Gesteinsbranche (Rudolf Ehmlich, Forum Rohstoffe)
12.00 Uhr	Mittagsessen im Hotelrestaurant
14.00 Uhr	Abfahrt zur Zementfabrikbesichtigung mit Rekrutierungsmaßnahmen mit anschließender
	kultureller Wanderung und Abendessen im Bürgergarten in Würzburg
18.00 Uhr	Rückfahrt zum Schloss Steinburg
22.00 Uhr	
Samstag, 16. September 2023 Abschied	

Figure 11. DEQ at Euroschotter, Germany.

2.2.5 ANEFA Young Entrepreneurs Committee

September 2023 saw the launch of the ANEFA Young Entrepreneurs Committee, an event to create a community and common space for all young aggregates-related entrepreneurs, share ideas about the present and future of aggregates, create networks and have a good time. In addition to exchanging experiences, creating links and sharing common ideas and solutions, ANEFA briefed how DEQ places the association at the forefront of mining.

Figure 12. DEQ at ANEFA Young Entrepreneurs Committee, Spain.

2.2.6 MADRID PLATFORM Hub Internacional de Negocios entre Europa y América Latina

Pierre Plaza presented the developments that Sigma Cognition is doing on IA in DEQ during the MADRID PLATFORM event held in Madrid in September 2023.

He explained together with José Eugenio Ortiz from the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM-AI), the Material Quality and Granulometry services in detail to the representative from Sociedad Minera Monte Alto from Chile.

Figure 13. DEQ at MADRID PLATFORM.

2.2.7 EFFE 12th World Conference on Explosives and Blasting

At the 12th World Conference on Explosives and Blasting held between the 9th and 12th of September 2023 in Dublin, Santiago Gómez (UPM-M) presented "JWL Equation of State applied to shock polar analysis", framed in the research activities carried out in the project.

Figure 14. DEQ at the 12th World Conference on Explosives and Blasting, Ireland.

2.2.1 Minerals Engineering 2024 Conference

Chalmers University and Montanuniversität Leoben's teams participated in the Minerals Engineering 2024 Conference held in Poland from the 14th to the 16th of September 2023. A presentation was made, and a paper was presented which can be read in section 2.1.3.

Figure 15. DEQ at Minerals Engineering.

2.2.2 ANDECE's decarbonisation conference

PC, César Luaces, participated in ANDECE's (Precast Concrete Industry Spanish Association) decarbonization conference held in October 2023 in Madrid, explaining the Neutral Aggregates 2050 Roadmap and why EPDs are important nowadays.

Figure 16. DEQ via Neutral Aggregates 2050 Roadmap presentation.

2.2.3 SBMI Branchdag

In October, Chalmers University Team explained at the Swedish Aggregates Producers Association Branch Day, in Gothenburg (Sweden), what EPDs are and how can they provide more value to producers in the future. An example of this is through digitalisation to enable data sharing throughout the production process that is being conducted in DEQ.

Figure 17. DEQ at SBMI Branchdag, Sweden.

2.2.4 Crowdhelix Annual RTO event

Hosted by Crowdhelix, a Horizon Europe participant, in October 2023 in Barcelona, ANEFA presented DEQ as an example of European networking and collaboration through open innovation.

Figure 18. DEQ at Crowdhelix RTO event, Spain.

2.2.5 Webinar Neutral Aggregates 2050 Roadmap

The presentation of the Spanish version of the Neutral Aggregates 2050 Roadmap was in October 2023. PC, César Luaces Frades, Director General of ANEFA, explained the main lines of the new Roadmap and its comprehensive and integrative vision.

This event was attended by the Deputy Director General of Mines from the Ministry for Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge of Spain.

Figure 19. DEQ via Neutral Aggregates 2050 Roadmap presentation.

2.2.6 FEDIEX

DEQ's PC attended and participated in the annual conference held in October 2023 of the Belgian Extractive Industry Federation titled 'The quarry sector: stakeholder of the energy transition'.

Figure 20. DEQ at FedieX, Belgium.

2.2.7 Seminar: Specialist in economic management of aggregate operations II

During the second edition of this seminar (October 2023) organised by ANEFA's Chair on Aggregates Technology for Sustainability of ETSI Minas de Madrid, aimed at entrepreneurs and managers of aggregates companies and operations throughout Spain, DEQ was again given as an example of good practice.

Figure 21. DEQ at Specialist in economic management of aggregate operations II seminar, Spain.

2.2.8 XVI Jornadas Técnicas ANIET

During the XVI Technical Conference of ANIET (November 2023), the National Association of the Extractive and Processing Industry of Portugal, topics such as the challenges for climate neutrality in the aggregates industry and the importance of raw materials for the energy, climate and digital transition were discussed.

Figure 22. DEQ at the XVI Technical Conference of ANIET, Portugal.

2.2.1 SMOPYC

ARCO set up a booth in SMOPYC 2023, the 19th International Show of Public Works Construction and Mining Machinery celebrated in Zaragoza, Spain, in November 2023.

Figure 23. DEQ at SMOPYC 2023, Spain.

ANEFA was also present explaining the project to those who approached the stand.

Figure 24. DEQ at SMOPYC 2023, Spain.

2.2.1 Minería digitalizada networking Forum

In November 2023, Paulo Romero, from the coordination team participated in an event organised by Centro Tecnológico del Mármol about digitalisation in the extractive industry.

Figure 25. DEQ at Minería Digitalizada Networking forum, Spain.

2.2.2 XV International Congress on Energy and Mineral Resources

ANEFA attended the XV International Congress on Energy and Mineral Resources held in the Spanish city of León between the 22nd and 24th of November 2023. It brought together more than 400 professionals from 150 companies and institutions, students, and technicians from the sector.

DEQ was very much present in this important event with a specific booth and an important presence at several round tables, sessions, and expositions. The members of the coordination team, and D&C leaders, introduced the project to the audience and presented the Consortium, the general aspects of the project, its goals, and its impact on the quarrying industry. Besides, Santiago Berjano, (General Directorate for Energy, Mining, and After Coal Development of the Autonomous Community of The Principality of Asturias) and José Eugenio Ortiz (clustering activities leader and UPM-AI team member) presented the role of their institutions in the project.

<https://www.congresominerialeon.org/programa-tecnico/>

Figure 26. DEQ at XV International Mining Congress, Spain.

2.2.3 Swedish Life Cycle Center: Network Conference

The Swedish Life Cycle Centre is a collaboration platform for academia, research institutes, industry and government agencies. During its Network conference, held in November 2023, the Chalmers University team displayed the following poster.

Figure 27. DEQ at Swedish Life Cycle Center, Sweden.

2.2.4 MBA lectures

PC, César Luaces lectures in an MBA programme majoring in mining and raw materials management from the Escuela de Organización Industrial. During his seminars, he has repeatedly explained the project and its implications in the industry. (<https://www.eoi.es/es/cursos/89560/mining-and-raw-materials-mba-sevilla>).

Figure 28. DEE at Escuela de Organización Industrial MBA programme, Spain.

2.2.1 DEQ's AI services for Chilean mining companies

In December 2023, Sigma’s and UPM-AI’s team made a presentation of the AI services to Chilean mining companies Creatialabs and Mototech. The objective was to understand the services and which ones could be offered in the mining Chilean context as it is different from Europe’s. In Chile, the most exploited mineral is copper and thus, the DEQ AI services application would be of a different nature in some cases but could be adapted.

From Sigma, Pierre Plaza, and Jacqueline Gomez Fraga were present. From UPM-AI, Jose Eugenio Ortiz was present. The agenda (Spanish) of the presentation was:

Tabla de contenidos	
La importancia de los agregados	
Objetivos del proyecto	
Captura de datos: almacenamiento y procesamiento	
Ubicación de los pilotos: ¿Porque?	
Arquitectura de datos y Roi de SIGMA	
Los retos de la plataforma de Datos	
Servicios IA (Sigma Cognition)	
Resultados:	Arquitectura de digitalización de datos Cálculo del volumen de las pilas mediante IA MetaQuarry (servicio de PLN) Detección de fallos mecánicos mediante IA Determinación de la calidad del material mediante IA
Lecciones Aprendidas	

Figure 29. The agenda of the presentation to the Chilean companies.

2.2.2 50th International Society of Explosives Engineers Annual Meeting

A DigiEcoQuarry party attended the 50th International Society of Explosives Engineers Annual Meeting in Savannah, Georgia, on January 24-27, 2024. Shown are from left to right, José A. Sanchidrián (UPM), Santiago Gómez (UPM), Juan Navarro (MAXAM), Tuomo Pirinen (SANDVIK) and Alberto Fernández (UPM).

Figure 30. DEQ at ISEE, USA.

2.2.3 AI services presentation at UMU

In February 2024, SIGMA’s team participated in an online conference at the Universidad de Murcia (Spain) for master’s degree students about Big Data and AI services practical industrial application.

Figure 31. DEQ at UMU Master's Degree.

2.2.4 PDAC 2024

Lorena Viladés, from the coordination team, once again joined the European Commission delegation attending the Prospectors & Developers Association of Canada (PDAC) 2024. This convention, held from the 3rd to the 6th of March in Toronto, Canada, is the world's most significant event dedicated to mining exploration and mining.

DIGIECOQUARRY took part in the convention alongside the European Executive Agency for Digital and Health (HaDEA), sharing space with representatives from the Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs (DG Growth), ambassadors, and other European institutions, aiming to showcase the EU's R&D efforts in the field of mining.

Figure 32. DEQ at PDAC 24, Canada.

2.2.5 Government of Asturias Conference

The PC, César Luaces and Diego Laza from about, alongside the General Director of Energy and Mining of the Government of Asturias and the General Director of the Asturian Energy Foundation, FAEN, presented DEQ at the headquarters of the Official College of Mining Engineers of North-western Spain in an event organised for the mining industry.

Figure 33. DEQ in Asturias, Spain.

2.2.6 ASGB Association Suisse de l'industrie des Graviers et du Béton

PO, César Luaces, presented the roadmap Neutral Aggregates 2050 in a conference organised by the Swiss Aggregates Association in March 2024.

Figure 34. DEQ at ASGB, Switzerland.

2.2.7 Forum of Latin American and Caribbean Countries on Sustainable Development 2024

In April 2024, ASOGRAVAS attended the Forum of Latin American and Caribbean Countries on Sustainable Development 2024, which was organized by ECLAC in Santiago, Chile. During a week, ASOGRAVAS participated in various meetings to gain a better understanding of the progress made towards achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in the region. Additionally, they learned about interesting advances in technology and digitalisation in mining, shared with the DIGIECOQUARRY project.

Figure 35. DEQ at Forum of Latin American and Caribbean Countries on Sustainable Development 2024, Chile.

2.2.8 Mining Geology and Mining Exploration Technologies Congress

UPM-AI attended the Mining Geology and Mining Exploration Technologies Congress held in Istanbul between the 2nd and 3rd of May 2024. It brought together professionals from companies and institutions, students, and technicians from the sector.

José Eugenio Ortiz (UPM-AI team) presented the oral communication “Digitalization in Aggregate Quarries” which was awarded for the best presentation.

2.3 DIGIECOQUARRY's workshops, seminars & panel presentations

2.3.1 Workshop: European Seminar on digitalisation of aggregates sites

ANEFA, in collaboration with the ANEFA Chair of Aggregates Technology for Sustainability of the Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros de Minas y Energía (Mining and Energy Engineering School) of the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid – UPM, organised a European Seminar on digitalisation of aggregate sites.

Figure 36 contains the programme, which consisted of nine sessions – all in English – each lasting between 45 and 60 minutes. To facilitate attendance, the workshop was hybrid: All of them could be followed via Zoom and three of them be in person at the ETSI Minas y Energía of Madrid.

<https://www.aridos.org/h2020-digiecoquarry-project/>

The dates on which the workshop was held were the 20th and 27th of March; the 3rd, 10th, 17th and 24th of April and the 8th of May. All of them started at 16.00 CET - Central European Time.

Registration was free and attendants were able to participate in the workshops of their choice, and they received a digital diploma certifying those workshops they attended.

digiecoquarry.eu
DEQ
DIGIECOQUARRY
 H2020 DIGIECOQUARRY PROJECT
The future of quarries

H2020 DigiEcoQuarry project: European Workshop on digitalisation in aggregates sites

Delivery format:
Hybrid: Videoconference and/or in-person
 (Fausto Eñuyar Classroom - E.T.S.I Minas y Energía de Madrid - Calle Ríos Rosas, 21 - 28003 Madrid, Spain)

Language: **English**

Free of charge.

Please register here to attend, receive the link, and obtain the certificate: [registration link]. You can register at any time, even after the Workshop has started.

Upon completion of the course, a diploma will be issued certifying attendance and participation in each successfully completed session.

Time: Central European Time – CET

ANEFA **IKERTEKKA** **Aridos**

Date	Time	Session	Organizer
20th March	16:00h - 16:50h	Session 1 ETSI Minas y Energía de Madrid & Online. H2020 DigiEcoQuarry project: Innovative Digital Sustainable Aggregates Systems.	ANEFA
27th March	16:00h - 16:45h	Session 2 ETSI Minas y Energía de Madrid & Online. Use cases of Artificial Intelligence in aggregate quarries and other quarrying and mining sites.	SIGMA & UPH-AE
3rd April	16:00h - 17:00h	Session 3 Online. Mobile equipment fleet management (part 1).	ABAUT.
10th April	16:00h - 17:30h	Session 5 ETSI Minas y Energía de Madrid & Online. Use case of Building Information Modeling (BIM) in quarrying and mining sites.	APP.
17th April	16:00h - 17:30h	Session 6 Online. Production control in mineral raw material processing plants (part 1).	Ho-estro.
24th April	16:00h - 16:45h	Session 8 Online. Data management and management platforms.	AKKODIS
24th April	16:00h - 16:45h	Session 9 Online. Digital tools for Environmental Product Declarations.	Chalmers University and RocTm.
24th April	16:00h - 16:45h	Session 10 Online. Production simulation models and digital twins in quarrying and mining sites.	MENTEK.
8th May	16:00h - 17:30h	Session 11 ETSI Minas y Energía de Madrid & Online. Development and integration of drilling and blasting technologies towards Industry 4.0.	UPH-M and MAXAM

Figure 36. European workshop on digitalisation in aggregates sites.

Table 1 states who led each workshop, what was it about and how many people attended it.

Table 1. Workshop sessions.

Session number	Led by	Attendees
1	Lorena Viladés (ANEFA)	40
2	José Eugenio Ortiz (UPM-AI)	45
3	Diego Laza (about)	32
5	Serdar Sadik (APP)	27
6	Alessandra Tarter, Andrea Bonatti, Andrea Ribezzo (MA-ESTRO)	26
8	Sadeq Zougari (AKKODIS)	34
9	Gauti Asbjörnsson, Christina Lee (Chalmers University)	30
10	Michael Odidi, William Shipman, Sandile Nkwananya (MINTEK)	31
11	José Ángel Sanchidrián (UPM-M), Juan Navarro (MAXAM)	46

Figure 37. J.E. Ortiz, J.A. Sanchidrián, J.Navarro and L.Viladés leading their workshops.

2.3.2 MOOC

The MOOC “Los áridos: minería, aplicación, digitalización y sostenibilidad”, a collaborative effort between UPM-AI, SIGMA, Zabala, and ANEFA, has already seen three successful runs.

The second edition kicked off on October 31st, 2023, wrapping up on December 24th with an impressive number of 80 participants. Following suit, the third edition commenced on March 4th, 2024, concluding on April 28th, boasting an even larger group of 110 eager learners.

Participants had the option to engage in either English or Spanish, making the course accessible to a wide audience. This MOOC comes at no cost, and successful completion of each module's tests earns participants a valuable certificate.

Figure 38. MOOC “Los áridos: minería, aplicación, digitalización y sostenibilidad”.

2.4 Online presence

2.4.1 Project's social media accounts & network with partner's social media profiles

Nowadays, social media profiles are considered key for the communication of the project. Since their creation, WP9 has been updating them by keeping up with DEQ's latest news and facts about the project.

DIGIECOQUARRY's social media URLs are:

- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/Digiecoquarry>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/digiecoquarry/>
- Instagram: [@digiecoquarry](https://www.instagram.com/digiecoquarry)
- Twitter: [@digi_eco](https://twitter.com/digi_eco)
- YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCdxXOC0k6kY5YEiW-sw1McA>
- Vimeo: <https://vimeo.com/digiecoquarry>

Direct access to DIGIECOQUARRY's social media is available on the website.

ANEFA administrates DIGIECOQUARRY's social media accounts, but all partners are required to actively interact with them, as well as to publish posts and news about DIGIECOQUARRY regularly through the social media of their organizations.

The partners' social media list is shown in *D9.1. Annex XVI*.

Further information, current status, figures, etc. can be seen in *D9.8 Dissemination and communication materials (3|3)*.

2.4.2 Videos

14 new videos have been uploaded to DEQ's YouTube channel and Vimeo. They are remarked in *D9.8 Dissemination and communication materials (3|3)*.

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCdxXOC0k6kY5YEiW-sw1McA>

2.4.3 Research Gate

An account in Research Gate has been created to share the scientific publications derived from the project.

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Digiecoquarry-Project>

Research Gate aims to connect the world of science and make research open to all. Twenty million researchers coming from diverse sectors in over 190 countries use this platform to connect, collaborate, and share their work. Since March 2023 the profile has had 1,975 downloads of the shared papers and conferences and 18 citations.

2.5 Other channels & tools

2.5.1 Partners' communication channels

DIGIECOQUARRY taps the support of partners' communication channels. During these months they have been publishing about the project in their social media, webpages, and intranets. Links to partners' publications are collected. The list of Partners' communication channels is shown in D9.1 Annex XIX.

- ANEFA:

<https://www.aridos.org/anefa-en-la-hannover-messe-con-digiecoquarry-y-rotate/>

<https://www.aridos.org/digiecoquarry-hace-los-deberes/>

<https://www.aridos.org/celebramos-2-anos-de-deq-avanzando-hacia-el-futuro/>

<https://www.aridos.org/segunda-edicion-del-mooc-sobre-aridos-sostenibilidad-y-digitalizacion/>

<https://www.aridos.org/anefa-en-el-xv-congreso-internacional-de-energia-recursos-minerales/>

<https://www.aridos.org/hoja-de-ruta-para-la-neutralidad-climatica-en-la-industria-de-los-aridos-aridos-sostenibles-innovadores-y-neutros/>

<https://www.aridos.org/deq-innovacion-en-canteras-y-encuentro-en-lisboa/>

<https://www.aridos.org/digiecoquarry-examen-pasado-con-nota/>

<https://www.aridos.org/digiecoquarry-se-presenta-en-asturias/>

<https://www.aridos.org/deq-datos-para-ser-mejores/>

<https://www.aridos.org/uno-de-los-equipos-deq-premiado-por-la-upm/>

<https://www.aridos.org/deq-digitalizacion-eficiencia-sostenibilidad/>

<https://www.aridos.org/deq-nuevo-curso-online-universitario-sobre-aridos/>

<https://www.aridos.org/deq-nuevos-videos-nuevas-herramientas-la-misma-estrategia/>

- ASOGRAVAS:

<https://x.com/asogravas/status/1656446509905223680?s=46>

<https://x.com/asogravas/status/1675901038027583493?s=46>

<https://x.com/asogravas/status/1676265321265545216?s=46>

<https://x.com/asogravas/status/1676259088026464256?s=46>

<https://x.com/asogravas/status/1696299249074319792?s=46>

<https://x.com/camaraprocemco/status/1696637871262695545?s=46>

<https://x.com/asogravas/status/1696672621377564995?s=46>

<https://x.com/asogravas/status/1699813648686858669?s=46>

<https://x.com/asogravas/status/1725241534390342001?s=46>

<https://x.com/asogravas/status/1734310955457093951?s=46>

<https://x.com/asogravas/status/1748002180706054342?s=46>

<https://x.com/asogravas/status/1719818207186284735?s=46>

https://fb.watch/rHQ_A51QdA/

<https://fb.watch/rHR1bTQ07/>

<https://fb.watch/rHR34ftHKe/>

2.5.2 Synergies with relevant projects and initiatives

DIGI-Raw and Sustainable CRMs4EU Projects' Cluster

Seven EU-funded projects in the field of mining, [MASTERMINE](#), [illuMINEation](#), [SUMEX](#), [ROBOMINERS](#), [Dig IT](#), [ROTATE](#) and DEQ have assembled Digi-Raw, a cluster formed to expand the impact of their work, streamline research, spark innovation, and build enduring partnerships.

DIGIECOQUARRY also participates in another cluster, called CRMs4EU, together with the PASSENGER, INSPIREE, REESILENCE, SALEMA, REPRODUCE, HARMONY, ReSilex AND ROTATE projects.

A dedicated space on DEQ's website has been created to share all the activities that may come out of these initiatives: <https://digiecoquarry.eu/alliances/>

Figure 39. DIGI-Raw cluster logo.

Figure 40. CRMs4EU cluster.

EU Green Week

The clustering event *How can EU-funded projects help to achieve a more sustainable, resilient and socially fair Europe* organized by ANEFA was framed within the European Green Week. It was moderated by Aggregates Europe - UEPG and there, two H2020, DIGIECOQUARRY and ROBOMINERS, and a Horizon Europe project, ROTATE, discussed how they address environmental challenges and engage citizens in their activities.

Figure 41. DEQ at EU Green Week.

Raw Materials Week

José Eugenio Ortiz, from the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid team, visited Brussels as part of the Raw Materials Week where he introduced the project to a mining sector and innovation-focused audience in a hybrid podium discussion organized by the ROBOMINERS project. Sister projects also from the European Commission Dig_IT, ROBOMINERS, illuMINEation, MasterMine Software, Inc., as well as UNEXMIN GeoRobotics Ltd also participated. Together they debated the latest technological developments to minimize the environmental impact of mineral extraction, the future of mining, technology uptake, and digitalisation in mining.

Figure 42. DEQ Raw Materials Week, Belgium.

Iberian Sustainable Mining Cluster clustering event

Also, during the XV Mining Congress of León, ANEFA took part in a clustering event organized by the Iberian Sustainable Mining Cluster along with other EU-funded projects such as S34I, MaDiTraCe, C-SINK Project, RESILEX, ECHO, TARANTULA, ROTATE, START, SEMACRET, and RAWMINA.

Figure 43. DEQ at ISMC clustering event.

2.5.3 Meetings with policymakers, external stakeholders and the IAB

ANEFA and WP8 Leader (UPM-AI) closely collaborate and coordinate the organisation of meetings with policymakers at EU and national levels. This aims to discuss potential issues and difficulties identified that could require political actions (policy, legislation or other).

All the results from the interaction with policymakers are reported in *D7.8: Evaluation report for Communications with policymakers (1|2)*.

On the other hand, the outcomes from the, as of today, three IAB meetings are detailed in *D8.3* and will be commented on *D8.4: Report on interactions with other organisations, projects and the IAB (1|2) and (2|2)*.

3 Conclusions

This document, titled “Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities (3|4)”, describes the articles, activities and all dissemination items related to DEQ that have been undertaken between months 24 and 36 of the project. This document will be last updated in month 48.

As it could be seen, Consortium partners have been very active in disseminating the project. Annex I contains a track record of all the activities carried out by each beneficiary.

4 References

The following references have been used for the preparation of this deliverable:

- D9.1: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan.
- DIGIECOQUARRY Grant Agreement number 101003750.

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Annex I. Partners' dissemination track record

Table 2. ANEFA's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: ANEFA		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		3
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
Digitalización en la industria de los áridos. Implantación, usos y Casos de éxito	https://www.sendaeventos.com/qrn/741428/docs/20882615112023134244.pdf	D9.9
Benchmarking y Cuadro de Mando Integral en el sector de los áridos. Traslado de las buenas prácticas y mejora continua	https://www.sendaeventos.com/qrn/741428/docs/78708115112023134030.pdf	D9.9
DIGIECOQUARRY: el futuro del sector de los áridos ya es el presente	https://www.sendaeventos.com/qrn/741428/docs/7314915112023131557.pdf	D9.9
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		4
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
VI Congreso Nacional de Áridos	May 2022, Spain	D9.4
XV International Congress on Energy and Minerals Resources 2023	November 2023, Spain	D9.9
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		4
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
Anefa actualidad. Jan - Feb - Mar 2021 issue	https://issuu.com/mythagosestudio/docs/anefa-actulidad_64	D9.3
Anefa actualidad. Apr – May – Jun 2021 issue	https://issuu.com/mythagosestudio/docs/anefa_65	D9.3
Anefa actualidad. Jul - Aug – Sep 2021 issue	https://issuu.com/mythagosestudio/docs/anefa66	D9.3
H2020 de la Comisión Europea aprueba financiar el proyecto DIGIECOQUARRY ideado y liderado por ANEFA	https://www.aridos.org/h2020-de-la-comision-europea-aprueba-financiar-el-proyecto-digiecoquarry-ideado-y-liderado-por-anefa/	D9.3
Arranca el proyecto DIGIECOQUARRY	https://www.aridos.org/arranca-el-proyecto-digiecoquarry/	D9.3

El "international Advisory Board" del Proyecto DIGIECOQUARRY	https://www.aridos.org/el-international-advisory-board-del-proyecto-digiecoquarry/	D9.3
Anefa actualidad. Oct - Nov – Dec 2021 issue	https://issuu.com/mythagosestudio/docs/anefaactualidad67	9.4
Anefa actualidad. Jan - Feb – Mar 2022 issue	https://issuu.com/mythagosestudio/docs/anefa_68_v2	9.4
Anefa actualidad. Apr - May – Jun 2022 issue	https://issuu.com/mythagosestudio/docs/anefa_actualidad_69	9.4
Anefa Online 179	https://www.aridos.org/novedades-en-el-proyecto-digiecoquarry/	9.4
Anefa Online 180	https://www.aridos.org/reunion-del-comite-tecnico-del-proyecto-digiecoquarry/	9.4
Anefa Online 181	https://www.aridos.org/digiecoquarry-empieza-a-tomar-forma-la-plataforma-para-la-gestion-inteligente-de-la-cantera/	9.4
Anefa Online 182	https://www.aridos.org/primer-hito-del-proyecto-digiecoquarry-superado/	9.4
Anefa Online 183	https://www.aridos.org/olimpiadas-y-sprints-finales/	9.4
Anefa Online 184	https://www.aridos.org/digiecoquarry-continua-su-trabajo-de-campo/	9.4
ANEFA Online 185	https://www.aridos.org/proyectos-europeos-firma-de-un-grant-agreement-inteligencia-artificial-broche-de-oro-y-un-premio/	9.6
ANEFA Online 188	https://www.aridos.org/cuenta-atras-para-milan/	9.6
ANEFA Online 189	https://www.aridos.org/digiecoquarry-celebra-su-reunion-anual-en-milan/	9.6
ANEFA Online 190	https://www.aridos.org/digiecoquarry-cierra-el-ano/	9.6
ANEFA Online 191	https://www.aridos.org/la-primera-version-de-los-data-lake-del-proyecto-deq-inicia-sus-pruebas-en-los-5-pilotos/	9.6
ANEFA Online 192	https://www.aridos.org/deq-en-valdilecha-nuevo-video/	9.6
ANEFA Online 193	https://www.aridos.org/anefa-en-el-evento-minero-mas-importante-del-mundo-liderando-deq-rotate/	9.6

	https://www.aridos.org/digiecoquarry-aprueba-con-nota-la-primer-revision-tecnica-de-la-comision-europea/	
Anefa actualidad. Jul – Aug – Sep 2022 issue	https://issuu.com/mythagosestudio/docs/ane_fa_70_ok	9.6
Anefa actualidad. Nov – Dec 2022 – Jan 2023 issue	https://issuu.com/mythagosestudio/docs/ane_fa_72_web_ab6a66ed2be600	9.6
Anefa actualidad. Feb – Mar 2023 issue	https://issuu.com/mythagosestudio/docs/ane_fa_73_web	9.6

4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS

Expected number of participations in events by M48		4
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
SMOPYC, International Show of Public Works, Construction and Mining Machinery	November 2021, Spain	D9.3
European Minerals Days	March 2022, Spain	D9.4
Jornadas de otoño - Emprendimiento e innovación hacia la sostenibilidad	September 2022, Spain	D9.6
BIMExpo	November 2022, Spain	D9.6
Seminar for Advancement of the Aggregate Industry	November 2022, Korea	D9.6
AFA Extremadura and Castilla La Mancha meetings	February 2023, Spain	D9.6
PDAC 2023	March 2023, Canada	D9.6
Webinar: AI, digitalization and the future of processes in quarries	March 2023, Spain-USA	D9.6
Hannover Messe 2023	April 2023, Germany	D9.6
Energy efficiency workshop	May 2023, Spain	D9.6
ANEFA's general assembly	May 2023, Spain	D9.6
Global Aggregates Information Network Summit	July 2023, New Zealand	D9.9
Euroschotter Conference	September 2023, Germany	D9.9
ANEFA Young Entrepreneurs Committee	September 2023, Germany	D9.9
ANDECE's decarbonisation conference	October 2023, Spain	D9.9
Crowdhelix Annual RTO event	October 2023, Spain	D9.9
Webinar Neutral Aggregates 2050 Roadmap	October 2023, Spain	D9.9
FEDIEX	October 2023, Spain	D9.9

Specialist in economic management of aggregate operations II	October 2023, Spain	D9.9
XVI Jornadas Técnicas ANIET	November 2023, Spain	D9.9
SMOPYC	November 2023, Spain	D9.9
Minería digitalizada networking Forum	November 2023, Spain	D9.9
PDAC 2024	March 2024, Canada	D9.9
Government of Asturias Conference	March 2024, Spain	D9.9
Association Suisse de l'industrie des Graviers et du Béton	March 2024, Spain	D9.9
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable
Interview with César Luaces Frades (PC) in Aggregates Business Europe		D9.3
Radio interview		D9.6
Neutral aggregates 2050		D9.9
MBA lectures		D9.9
Workshop: European Seminar on digitalisation of aggregates sites		D9.9

Table 3. GRANULATS VICAT's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: GRANULATS VICAT		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48	0	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48	1	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48	1	
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
5. OTHER		
Action	Details in Deliverable	

Table 4. CEMEX's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: HANSON		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48	0	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48	1	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48	1	
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
5. OTHER		
Action	Details in Deliverable	

Table 5. HOLCIM's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: HOLCIM		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		0
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		1
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
VI Congreso Nacional de Áridos	May 2022, Spain	D9.4
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
Lanciato Digiecoquarry: il Progetto chiave per la digitalizzazione del settore degli Aggregati	https://concretenews.it/2021/06/11/lanciato-digiecoquarry-il-progetto-chiave-per-la-digitalizzazione-del-settore-degli-aggregati/	D9.3
	https://www.edizionipei.it/notizie/news/lanciato-digiecoquarry-il-progetto-chiave-per-la-digitalizzazione-del-settore-degli-aggregati.htm	D9.3
	https://www.gowem.it/DigiEcoQuarry-Holcim	D9.3
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
ANEPLA assembly	November 2022, Italy	D9.6
Workshop Holcim	March 2023, Italy	D9.6
Workshop at SaMoTer w/ Ma-Estro	May 2023, Italy	D9.6
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable

Table 6. CSI's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: CSI		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48	0	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48	1	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48	1	
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
Andesit „Gestein des Jahres 2020/21	September 2021	D9.6
5. OTHER		
Action	Details in Deliverable	

Table 7. CIMPOR's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: CIMPOR		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48	0	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48	1	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48	1	
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
Tektónica fair	May 2023, Portugal	D9.9
5. OTHER		
Action	Details in Deliverable	

Table 8. SANDVIK's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: SANDVIK		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48	2	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
VI Congreso Nacional de Áridos	May 2022, Spain	D9.4
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48	1	
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
5. OTHER		
Action	Details in Deliverable	

Table 9. METSO OUTOTEC's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: METSO OUTOTEC		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48	2	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48	1	
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
5. OTHER		
Action	Details in Deliverable	

Table 10. MAXAM's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: MAXAM		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
A novel borehole surveying system for underground mining: Design and performance assessment	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0263224122002895	D9.4
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
MAXAM announces its participation in the DIGIECOQUARRY project	https://www.maxamcorp.com/en/newsinsights/news/maxamannouncesparticipationdigiecoquarry	D9.3
Maxam is focusing on customer solutions	https://www.quarrymagazine.com/2022/11/14/maxam-is-focusing-on-customer-solutions/	D9.6
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
Energy efficiency workshop	May 2023, Spain	D9.6
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable
Workshop: European Seminar on digitalisation of aggregates sites		D9.9

Table 11. ITK's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: ITK		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48	2	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48	1	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
MIRO Forum	November 2021, Germany	D9.3
BAUMA 22	October 2022, Germany	D9.6
Steinexpo	August 2023, Germany	D9.9 c
5. OTHER		
Action	Details in Deliverable	

Table 12. MONTANUNIVERSITÄT LEOBEN'S dissemination track record.

PARTNER: MONTANUNIVERSITÄT LEOBEN		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		3
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
Digitalisation for a more sustainable mining industry	https://www.unileoben.ac.at/en/newsdetail/durc-h-digitalisierung-zu-einem-nachhaltigerem-bergbau/	D9.3
Stein und Kies	Paper	D9.4
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
Sustainable Development in the Minerals Industry - SDIMI 2022	September 2022, South Africa	D9.6
26th World Mining Congress	June 2023, Australia	D9.9
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable

Table 13. CHALMERS' dissemination track record.

PARTNER: CHALMERS		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48	3	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
Development of Production and Environmental Platforms for the European Aggregates and Minerals Industries	https://www.min-eng.com/sustainableminerals23/drafts/session3/asbjornsson.pdf	D9.9
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48	2	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
IMPC Asia-Pacific 2022	August 2022, Australia	D9.6
Minerals Engineering 2024 Conference	February 2024, Sweden	D9.9
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
Stenkoll	paper	D9.6
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48	1	
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
SMBI Production I	November 2022, Sweden	D9.6
Swedish Mining Innovation PhD Student Network workshop	November 2022, Sweden	D9.6
New standards for circular economy in the construction industry	August 2023, Sweden	D9.9
SBMI Branchdag	October 2023, Sweden	D9.9
Swedish Life Cycle Center: Network Conference	November 2023, Sweden	D9.9
5. OTHER		
Action	Details in Deliverable	

Workshop: European Seminar on digitalisation of aggregates sites

D9.9

Table 14. UPM-M's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: UPM-M		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		3
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
A novel borehole surveying system for underground mining: Design and performance assessment	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0263224122002895	D9.4
On the Influence of Sampling Scale on the In Situ Block Size Distribution	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00603-022-02953-1	D9.6
A Non-parametric Discrete Fracture Network	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00603-022-03194-y	D9.6
Mechanically operated probe to survey ring-blastholes in a safe and efficient way	Fragblast Conference 2022	D9.6
Shock Impedance Method Applied to Detonation Pressure Measurements	49th Annual Conference on Explosives and Blasting Technique ISEE	D9.6
A comparative study of backbreak distance prediction in the open-pit mine based on support vector regression and bio-inspired metaheuristic algorithms.	4th International Symposium of Machine Learning and Big Data in Geoscience	D9.9
JWL Equation of State applied to shock polar analysis.	Conference paper 12th World Conference on Explosives and Blasting	D9.9
Impedance Method Applied to Detonation Pressure Measurements	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369040480_Shock_Impedance_Method_Applied_to_Detonation_Pressure_Measurements	D9.9
Full-field solution from an oblique shock to estimate ground motion from blasting	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijrmmms.2024.105688	D9.9
A Method for Reconstruction of Size Distributions from 3D Drone Image Analysis: A Case Study	https://doi.org/10.1007/s00603-024-03765-1	D9.9
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
VI Congreso Nacional de Áridos	May 2022, Spain	D9.4
Fragblast 13	October 2022, China	D9.6

ISEE Annual Conference on Explosives and Blasting	February 2022, Las Vegas, USA	D9.6
ISEE Annual Conference on Explosives and Blasting	February 2023, San Antonio, USA	D9.6
4th International Symposium of Machine Learning and Big Data in Geoscience	September 2023, Cork, Ireland	D9.9
EFFE 12th World Conference on Explosives and Blasting	September 2023, Dublin, Ireland	D9.9
ISEE Annual Conference on Explosives and Blasting	January 2024, Savannah, GA, USA	D9.9
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable
Workshop: European Seminar on digitalisation of aggregates sites		D9.9

Table 15. UPM-AI's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: UPM-AI		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		3
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
Geochemical characterization of geological lacustrine formations in Central Spain	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369260714_Geochemical_characterization_of_geological_lacustrine_formations_in_Central_Spain	D9.6
La digitalización de minerales y rocas para la enseñanza virtual de Geología	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369260141_Digitalizacion_de_minerales_y_rocas_para_la_ensenanza_virtual_de_la_Geologia	D9.6
La enseñanza virtual de geología y minería a través de MOOCS	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369260294_LA_ENSEANZA_VIRTUAL_DE_GEOLOGIA_Y_MINERIA_A_TRAVES_DE_MOOCS	D9.6
Modelos geológicos 3D y digitalización de afloramientos	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369260405_MODELOS_GEOLOGICOS_3D_Y_DIGITALIZACION_DE_AFLORAMIENTOS	D9.6
Acercando los autocodificadores variacionales al gran público	https://documentacion.sea-acustica.es/publicaciones/Elche22/ID-55.pdf	9.6
Radiofrequency absorbance as a novel concentration indicator in sucrose aqueous solutions	https://revistas.unal.edu.co/index.php/ingenv/article/view/94695	9.6
IA para el mantenimiento predictivo en canteras. Modelado	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/375289583_IA_para_el_mantenimiento_predictivo_en_canteras_modelado	D9.9
Expanding the Frontiers of Web Audio With Autoencoders and JavaScript	https://oa.upm.es/77104/1/JAES-D-22-00045_LR.pdf	D9.9
Phase-Aware Transformations in Variational Autoencoders for Audio Effects	https://oa.upm.es/77103/1/JAES-D-22-00016_LR.pdf	D9.9
Generación de efectos de audio para cine con inteligencia artificial	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/375289585_FOLEY-VAE_GENERACION_DE_EFECTOS_DE_AUDIO_PARA_CINE_CON_INTELIGENCIA_ARTIFICIAL	D9.9
Del visual al auditivo: sonorización de escenas guiada por imagen	https://oa.upm.es/78660/1/paper_tecniacusticaria.pdf	D9.9
Digitalisation in aggregate quarries (La digitalización en las explotaciones de áridos).	https://www.sendaeventos.com/qrn/741428/docs/4042311092023203002.pdf	D9.9
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2

Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
XIII Iberian Geochemical Congress	April 2022, Spain	D9.4
VI Congreso Nacional de Áridos	May 2022, Spain	D9.4
X USATIC International Congress	June 2022, Spain	D9.6
FECIES	September 2022, Spain	D9.6
TECNIACÚSTICA 2022 (53º International conference of acoustic technologies)	November 2022, Spain	D9.6
XV International Congress on Energy and Minerals Resources 2023	November 2023, Spain	D9.9
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
JRC / HaDEA Technical Workshop "Channelling knowledge from European projects into the Raw Materials Information System"	December 2021	D9.4
Spanish Geology Olympics	March 2022, Spain	D9.4
Expominerals	March 2022, Spain	D9.4
Field trips of the School of Mines and Energy of Madrid	April 2022, Spain	D9.4
Spanish Science Week	November 2022, Spain	D9.6
Spanish Science Week	November 2022, Spain	D9.6
MADRID PLATFORM Hub Internacional de Negocios entre Europa y América Latina	September 2023, Spain	D9.9
DEQ's AI services for Chilean mining companies	December 2023, Spain	D9.9
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable
Workshop: European Seminar on digitalisation of aggregates sites		D9.9

Table 16. AKKODIS's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: AKKODIS		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
Development of Production and Environmental Platforms for the European Aggregates and Minerals Industries	https://www.min-eng.com/sustainableminerals23/drafts/session3/asbjornsson.pdf	D9.9
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48	2	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48	1	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
5. OTHER		
Action	Details in Deliverable	
Workshop: European Seminar on digitalisation of aggregates sites	D9.9	

Table 17. ARCO's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: ARCO		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		0
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
VI Congreso Nacional de Áridos	May 2022, Spain	D9.4
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		2
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
Participación Proyecto DIGIECOQUARRY	https://www.arcoelectronica.es/noticias/participacion-proyecto-digiecoquarry/	D9.3
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
SMOPYC	November 2023, Spain	D9.9
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable

Table 18. MAESTRO's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: MAESTRO		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		0
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		2
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
SaMoTer	May 2023, Italy	D9.6
Workshop at SaMoTer w/ Holcim Italy	May 2023, Italy	D9.6
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable
Workshop: European Seminar on digitalisation of aggregates sites		D9.9

Table 19. DH&P's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: DH&P		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
MIRO Forum 21	November. Berlin, Germany	D9.4
MIRO Forum 22	November. Berlin, Germany	D9.6
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable

Table 20. ABAUT's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: ABAUT		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48	2	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
VI Congreso Nacional de Áridos	May 2022, Spain	D9.4
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48	1	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
5. OTHER		
Action	Details in Deliverable	
Workshop: European Seminar on digitalisation of aggregates sites	D9.9	

Table 21. APP's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: APP		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48	2	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48	1	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
BIMExpo	November 2022, Spain	D9.6
5. OTHER		
Action	Details in Deliverable	
Workshop: European Seminar on digitalisation of aggregates sites	D9.9	

Table 22. SIGMA's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: SIGMA		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
Sigma cognition	https://sigmacognition.ai/digiecoquarry/	D9.4
Design and Usage Example of a Data Warehouse in the Context of the DigiEcoQuarry Project by	paper	D9.6
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the event	Date	Details in Deliverable
Webinar: AI, digitalization and the future of processes in quarries	March 2023, Spain-USA	D9.6
MADRID PLATFORM Hub Internacional de Negocios entre Europa y América Latina	September 2023, Spain	D9.9
DEQ's AI services for Chilean mining companies	December 2023, Spain	D9.9
AI services presentation at UMU	February 2024, Spain	D9.9
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable

Table 23. DGASTUR's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: DGASTUR		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48		0
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
El proyecto europeo H2020 – DIGIECOQUARRY en el marco estratégico del suministro de materias primas minerales	https://www.sendaeventos.com/qrn/741428/docs/5400320112023094517.pdf	D9.9
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48		2
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48		1
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
Arranca el Proyecto DIGIECOQUARRY	https://www.faen.es/arranca-el-proyecto-digiecoquarry/	D9.3
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48		1
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
5. OTHER		
Action		Details in Deliverable

Table 24. ASOGRAVAS's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: ASOGRAVAS		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48	3	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48	1	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
Sexto Encuentro Nacional de la Industria de Agregados	September 2022, Colombia	D9.6
MaPric	November 2022, Chile	D9.6
Expomin 2023	April 2023, Chile	D9.6
Global Aggregates Information Network Summit	July 2023, New Zealand	D9.9
12 th Concrete Pavement Congress	May 2023, Colombia	D9.9
5 ^o Internacional Concrete Sustainability Conference	August 2023, Colombia	D9.9
IV Seminario Internacional de Minería y Planeamiento Minero	August 2023, Colombia	D9.9
Forum of Latin American and Caribbean Countries on Sustainable Development 2024	April 2024, Chile	D9.9

5. OTHER	
Action	Details in Deliverable

Table 25. MINTEK's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: MINTEK		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48	2	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48	1	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
Joint Research Centre (JRC) Training Webinar	October 2021	D9.4
South African Institute of Quarrying Conference	March 2022, South Africa	D.4
5. OTHER		
Action	Details in Deliverable	
Workshop: European Seminar on digitalisation of aggregates sites	D9.9	

Table 26. ROCTIM's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: ROCTIM		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48	0	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
Development of Production and Environmental Platforms for the European Aggregates and Minerals Industries	https://www.min-eng.com/sustainableminerals23/drafts/session3/asbjornsson.pdf	D9.9
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48	2	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48	1	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48	1	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
5. OTHER		
Action	Details in Deliverable	
Workshop: European Seminar on digitalisation of aggregates sites	D9.9	

Table 27. ZABALA's dissemination track record.

PARTNER: ZABALA		
1. SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
Expected number of publications by M48	0	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
2. SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES		
Expected number of participations in scientific conferences by M48	0	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
3. JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES		
Expected number of articles by M48	0	
Title	Link	Details in Deliverable
4. EVENTS, FAIRS AND WORKSHOPS		
Expected number of participations in events by M48	2	
Name of the conference	Date	Details in Deliverable
5. OTHER		
Action	Details in Deliverable	